

Development & Reliable Orchestration of Network Applications for the Automotive Domain Across the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum

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Abstract—The latest advancements in mobile networks, extending beyond the 5G trends, have had a substantial impact on the vertical automotive sector. These advancements have empowered the development of Network Applications and simplified the provision of new services. Container orchestration technologies allow deploying highly distributed services, spanning from the cloud to far-edge devices embedded in vehicles (i.e., the On Board Units). Requirements like high availability and reliability are usually critical for automotive services, as they are heavily affected by any potential discontinuity in mobile connectivity.

The 5G-IANA Framework simplifies the development and testing of Network Applications capable to exploit the reliability of 5G networks. It provides a multi-domain orchestration system for zero-touch provisioning and configuration of Network Applications over multi-cluster computing infrastructures extended towards edge resources and far-edge devices. This paper presents the orchestration system, analyzing its role in the 5G-IANA Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) and its involvement in conducting trials to evaluate automotive services by third-party experimenters. Additionally, it provides a description of an Automotive Network Application running on Nokia's 5G infrastructure, which hosts both an instance of the platform and the applications deployed on top of it.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of 'Network Application (nApp)' is relatively new, significantly enforced by the European Commission through the ICT-41 call, which has provided an approach to its definition: 'Virtual Network Functions (VNF) may be chained across several domains to create Network Applications (nApps) tailored to the requirements of specific tenants' [1]. The 5G-IANA platform aims to simplify and homogenize the processes of crafting, on-boarding, and managing Network Applications. Its objective is to unlock the capability for automotive application/service providers to enable their own services, thereby reducing the complexity involved and providing them access to 5G resources such as radio, core, MEC, OBUs, and RSUs resources.

One crucial feature of the 5G-IANA platform is, therefore, the development, orchestration and management of Network Applications. This consists of two complementary procedures: a) the lifecycle management of a Network Application from

the application point of view, namely the processing of a "high-level" request from an automotive vertical service provider and its subsequent dynamic on-the-fly deployment and adaptation to its service requirements, and b) the lifecycle management of the Network Application from the network point of view.

5G-IANA aims to provide a novel experimentation platform to make third parties, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive domain, able to execute trials on top of it through the development, deployment, and testing of their services. The experimentation platform is composed of a set of hardware and software tools providing the infrastructure required to run reliable distributed services, as well as the management and orchestration components for the design, onboard, and orchestration of automotive-specific Network Applications.

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP): service development relies on the 5G-IANA Network Application (nApp) Framework, which provides a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for securely enabling the deployment of end-to-end network services across the Edge/Far edge-to-Cloud continuum infrastructure offered by the platform. To ensure reliability and high-availability of the services, a MicroK8s-based [2] orchestrator has been designed to fulfill the Automotive vertical requirements and constraints, which are usually composed of on-boarded devices heavily affected by any potential discontinuity in mobile connectivity. A Distributed Machine Learning (DML) system provides the functionalities to manage and orchestrate ML-based Network workloads, enabling the development and deployment of cutting-edge applications onboarded in the new generation of vehicles. The data to feed the DML Orchestrator are collected through a distributed data collection platform that monitors both infrastructure metrics (such as computing resources and network performance) and vertical service-specific metrics. Combining machine learning with network orchestration shows a forward-thinking approach, using data insights for smart decision-making and demonstrating how innovation meets practical use in the automotive industry.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The 5G-IANA platform supports the integration of orchestration on top of OBUs, based on Kubernetes, for offering a more flexible and scalable management of Network Applications. Kubernetes [3] is an open-source container orchestration system for automating application deployment, service discovery, and scaling/load balancing/traffic distribution. For edge-based environments, Kubernetes can be useful for orchestrating and scheduling resources, managing and deploying edge devices, and coordinating cloud configurations from the cloud to edge data center workloads. In this way, automotive application developers can create their Network Applications following a conventional microservices-based approach where each component can be independently orchestrated.

The orchestration of applications on OBUs is not a common feature that is typically provided in commercial devices. The analysis of publicly available leaflets and datasheets indicates that commercial OBUs currently do not seem to provide this feature. A key requirement of the OBUs for enabling the orchestration of applications is to support virtualized or containerized applications. This aspect also seems not to be tackled in commercial OBUs.

Solutions for orchestrating applications have been introduced in several research projects together with different virtualization approaches. The use of virtualization in the automotive domain and on the OBUs has been proposed in [4]. An OBU that supports Docker containerization has been introduced in [5]. This solution is particularly relevant as Kubernetes exploits containers for orchestrating the applications. The 5GinFIRE project [6] proposed an orchestration solution that is close to the 5G-IANA concept. In the 5GinFIRE project, a multi-site orchestrator was developed exploiting the functionalities provided by Open Source MANO. The orchestrator was then used to deploy automotive applications as Virtual Network Functions on real OBU hardware devices.

Since the Network Application concept is fairly new, there are not many research works identified in the literature, with most being driven by relative EU projects. For instance, the VITAL-5G project defines the Network Application as a fundamental building block of the Transport & Logistics (T&L) vertical service chain, with the objective to hide the complexity beneath the application layer, while imposing service-level requirements with respect to 5G [7]. In this sense, the notion of a Network Application in this work is similar to the one presented in this paper. In 5G-INDUCE, an nApp Orchestration component is integrated into the Operations Support System (OSS) and offers the interfacing between the Network Application's service requests and the actually assigned resources and network connectivity offerings [8]. At the same time, the network operator is able to apply policies and any intelligent data analytics at the service level, while the application orchestration and the pure OSS processes are clearly separated. Finally, in 5GASP, a Service Orchestrator is in charge of transforming the so-called Network Slice Template properties into network requirements that should be met by the 5G network, mainly through network slicing [9].

III. CLOUD NATIVE ORIENTED NAPP MODELING

A nApp is a composition of atomic components (Application Functions to implement the logic of a service and Network

Fig. 1. The 5G-IANA Automotive experimentation platform

Functions for its communication and networking tasks) that exploits the 5G services (like localization, low latency, etc.) and can be deployed over a 5G infrastructure. These components are usually delivered through Docker Containers, which can be instantiated separately depending on the requirements.

A Network Application is defined by its nApp package, a reusable descriptor that includes service-level information and defines how the application and its components can be shared and reused. The creation of automotive-oriented Network Applications starts with the development of their atomic components, i.e., microservices to be deployed and orchestrated in the distributed 5G-IANA MicroK8s-based infrastructure, mainly to be hosted in the Far Edge resources on the OBUs/RSUs. Chaining nApps allows developers to create scalable containerized applications for advanced end-to-end vertical services using the 5G-IANA orchestration platform.

A. nApp development framework

The 5G-IANA development framework (the nApp Toolkit) is composed of two main functional blocks: the nApp Catalogue and the Vertical App Composition and Customization. The nApp Catalogue provides a set of features to support nApp package management, Application Function (AF) and Network Function (NF) management. It includes nApp package management, which offers all the functionalities to store, query, update, and delete nApp packages so that they can be reused several times in different contexts and with different requirements. Additionally, it includes a centralized registry to store the artifacts (i.e., the Docker Images). A nApp package (stored in the catalogue) includes a nApp template, which is a description for the application containing the information to query, chain, customize, and deploy the nApp with the features made available by the 5G-IANA development framework and the 5G-IANA Application Orchestrator. A nApp package also includes the documentation needed by the developer to use the nApp and the licenses associated with the application. The 5G-IANA development framework offers the developer a set of "nApp starter kits," which are nApps already defined and made available to the developers as a starting point to compose Vertical Services.

An application developer, using the Vertical App Composition and Customization, retrieves the available nApps from the nApp catalogue to graphically link together several atomic

components to form a Network Application. Alternatively, he can link atomic components with other nApps to compose a more complex vertical service.

These elements, retrieved from the catalogue, are instantiated in the 5G-IANA development framework. The instantiation involves specifying the exposed interfaces used to communicate, the required high-level QoS parameters, the required 5G services to be used, and the KPIs that should be used to evaluate the performance of the deployed service.

B. DevOps procedures for nApp Delivery & Publishing

A programmer aiming to create an automotive-focused nApp has two operational approaches: a) he can compose directly the application by manually creating the template and committing it on the version control system used by the DevOps platform, b) he can use the graphical composer provided by the 5G-IANA platform to graphically link together the atomic components and the nApps, which are made available in the 5G-IANA nApp catalogue. A repository update event triggers a CI/CD pipeline that analyzes the nApp template. Subsequently, it builds the components used in the application or in the vertical service. Once this process is complete, the template is validated and onboarded to the 5G-IANA nApp catalogue.

This procedure ensures the integrity of each Network Application onboarded on the platform catalogue, exposing them for use by the Application Orchestrator. Developers can link Network Applications together to create a standalone end-to-end service that fulfills the vertical service requirements. A developer links together two Network Applications in the same way as linking two atomic components, using the input and output interfaces documented in each component's repository. The DevOps procedures in 5G-IANA have been studied and tested using the Gitlab platform; however, this approach could be applied to any generic DevOps platform.

IV. NAPP ORCHESTRATION & VALIDATION

The Application Orchestrator (AO) administrative domain is responsible for registering a Network Application and all its components, providing cloud-related and slice-related metadata, authoring deployment and runtime policies, negotiating slices and managing the operational state of the nApp within the scope of a materialized slice. On the other hand, the Resource Management domain is responsible for materializing a slice based on a request, thus coordinating all activities that transform bare-metal and virtual resources into a programmable environment that can be used by service providers through the AO and nApp Toolkit.

The aim of AO (including nApp Toolkit) is: a) to assist the service providers wrap cloud native nApp in a proper format, so as to be publishable and reusable in the Container Registry and b) to provide a uniform way for nApps deployment and management over the programmable resources by abstracting infrastructure specific information.

Moreover, AO is responsible for the deploying and maintaining the equilibrium of the nApp during its operational state. It operates on top of industry dominant container and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) cloud platforms (specifically Kubernetes, Openstack). This is achieved by handling the communication

and the programmability with the underlying infrastructure. This way it provides a thin layer of abstraction to the service user since it totally disengages him from infrastructure specific information. As stated above, the aim of the nApp Toolkit is to assist the service providers wrap cloud native nApps in a proper format and to form a valid nApp, so as to be publishable in the Container Registry. Afterwards, the nApp definition which is reflected as a stored template, is being consumed by the AO which translates that in specific descriptors depending on the identified underlying infrastructure. After that the initial deployment takes place. The initial state of the deployment that can be disrupted. Initial state refers to the amount of resources that are allocated per component of the nApp, the slice parameters that have been selected, the geographical constraints of the deployment, etc., the amount of instances per component. Each of these aspects serves a different functional purpose. Any change to the operational state of a nApp has to be reflected on respective control-plane signalling. AO responsible for materializing these changes and orchestrating all steps, in order for the new equilibrium to be maintained.

A. Distributed Infrastructure for Cloud Native Automotive Services

The 5G-IANA project aims to provide a distributed infrastructure that ranges from cloud to edge servers, and to far-edge devices (i.e., OBUs and RSUs) to realize a continuum infrastructure on which is possible to deploy applications implementing different automotive services. Figure 2 illustrates the schema of the distributed infrastructure with the main 5G-IANA platform modules.

This infrastructure exploits Kubernetes for the automatic orchestration and deployment of applications. Kubernetes allows users to perform the deployment, management, and scale applications in a cluster environment. Furthermore, Kubernetes offers additional features, such as automated provisioning, self-healing, scalability and resource optimization, that are of interest in the context of the 5G-IANA project.

There are different distributions of Kubernetes available. In the 5G-IANA project, the Microk8s distribution has been selected as the most suited for the scope. Microk8s is a Kubernetes distribution that is certified by Canonical. It implements all the main features of Kubernetes and it is designed to be

Fig. 2. The 5G-IANA Distributed Infrastructure schema

Fig. 3. Closed Loop Orchestration mechanism implemented by the AOEP platform components

lightweight and easy to install. These peculiar characteristics made Microk8s be suitable for 5G-IANA as devices with limited hardware capabilities (e.g., ARM-based) are considered within the project. It is then preferable to have a solution that does not consume extensively the available computational power. Furthermore, Microk8s makes it possible to execute nApps in the master nodes if the workers are overloaded. This feature may further relax the hardware constraints of far-edge devices.

The 5G-IANA infrastructure deploys Microk8s with an architecture based on distributed multi-cluster approach. This involves running multiple clusters in different regions or cloud providers and improves the platform’s scalability and availability. Furthermore, it is also possible to reduce the overall latency if a far-edge device (e.g., OBU) connects to the closest cluster. This approach is also convenient to define different clusters in which it is possible to isolate far-edge devices belonging to specific vendors or entities.

The distributed approach of the selected architecture involves having a distributed control plane that increases its availability. Indeed, a cluster has multiple masters, both at the cloud, and edge level, in order to avoid single points of failure. A possible drawback of this approach could be the redundant computational resources that are required to deploy multiple master nodes together with the complexity of the management.

B. Policy Based Action Enforcement

The services’ lifecycle management of the 5G-IANA platform (depicted in Figure 3) provides encapsulates runtime policies. The user of the platform can define and apply policies using a decision-making engine to reschedule deployments and operations, like migration and scaling. This is achieved by a modular component namely Policy Engine (PE), that is integrated in the 5G-IANA architecture. The Policies Engine provides Service Level Agreement (SLA) and policy imposition over the deployed nApps. This is realized through a rule-based framework that attempts to derive execution instructions based on the current set of data and the active rules. The rules are associated with the deployed nApp at

each point of time. The term “set of data” implies that the PE is connected with a source of monitoring data, thus the centralized monitoring entity of the 5G-IANA Platform that controls the data monitoring and collection process through a set of passive monitoring probes. The concept of SLA and policy imposition follows the next approach: after the deployment of a nApp and the imposition of a policy, a set of monitoring metrics are collected and processed. The collected metrics are related with the specific nApp and the processing of those is done according to a set of expressions defined in the policies. The metrics and the corresponding expressions may regard indicative component specific metrics, nApp specific KPIs or operational metrics. After the processing of the collected data, one or more alerts are triggered and these alerts are published in a pub/sub message queue and can be consumed by the PE. PE realizes inference over the defined set of rule and produces actions. The actions from the inference results are then published to a pub/sub message queue and can be consumed by other systems (like the orchestration loop or other integrated modules).

C. nApps Data and Resource Monitoring in the Distributed Infrastructure

The 5G-IANA platform foresees two modules that are responsible for monitoring the infrastructure’s status and the applications deployed: the “Monitoring and Analytics” (M&A) and the “Distributed Data Collection” (DDC) modules. These modules allow the collection and processing of information from the running vertical services during the runtime. Figure 2 depicts the flows of collected data from the distributed infrastructure to these two modules. The M&A module is in charge to monitor the runtime environment of the deployed automotive vertical services. It continuously monitors different metrics that are defined according to specific policies. The DDC module provides the means to specify these policies and to define the metrics that are specific to each vertical service. This approach provides the required flexibility to adapt the monitoring to the needs of the deployed vertical service.

The DCC module is also in charge to monitor the implemented network slices, the available infrastructure and virtual resources. The DCC monitors all those metrics, related to network slices, that are provided by the 5G network services. The monitoring of the virtual infrastructure provides indications about the available resources and their current consumption. The DCC also controls the virtual resources by providing details about the resource usage for a specific container implementing a given function.

The information collected by the DCC can be processed by the M&A module using a data analytics-based approach. The M&A data analytics engine is implemented by a management system that exploits forward and backward chaining inferences. This approach enables the analysis of data and the management of the system according to defined rules.

The monitoring information is also made available to relevant nApps through open interfaces for better management and real-time configuration of the relevant automotive vertical services. The availability of monitoring data is useful to nApps developers for understanding the behaviour of the nApp over time. The developers can profile the consumption of resources to identify bottlenecks from a network and computing perspective.

Fig. 4. The procedure to register a new Edge/Far Edge cluster, to notify the availability/unavailability of a node and how the Resource Inventory is queried by the VAO

D. DML Orchestration

The 5G-IANA orchestration platform pays particular attention to the support and facilitation of Machine Learning (ML) workloads that are increasingly emerging in the vertical automotive domain for services such as Predictive Maintenance, Trajectory Planning, Predictive QoS. In this context, the platform integrates a Distributed ML Orchestration (DMLO) component responsible for various ML-oriented primitive management and orchestration functions (see [10]), including Client Selection for Federated Learning [11] workloads. This corresponds to a multi-parameter client selection scheme, based on both ML-specific (e.g., feature availability, data entropy, data freshness, etc.) and generic (connectivity, processing capacity, location, etc.) client criteria. In the context of the automotive domain, this functionality translates to the identification and selection of the most appropriate set of vehicles to participate a Federated Learning training round subject to the aforementioned criteria. The target is to abstract this functionality and offer it to vertical service providers, thus: (i) alleviating vertical service providers from the need to integrate this functionality in each and every FL-based service; (ii) allowing a more efficient implementation, building on the inherent ability of the 5G-IANA platform to monitor the status of the far edge (OBU) resources; (iii) enabling a more efficient use of OBU resources, by allowing client selection decisions to be translated to service life-cycle-management events by the platform e.g., de-activate a FL-training client when no data are available.

E. Service Driven Slice Management and Resource Orchestration

The Slice Manager & Resource Orchestration module provides the mechanisms to translate the high-level service instantiation requirements provided by the Vertical Application Orchestrator to a detailed set of information about: (i) the appropriate 5G Network Slice Profile associated with a Network Slice Instance (NSI), (ii) the appropriate compute

resource quotas across the target virtualized infrastructure segments for running the Vertical Service components, i.e., the Automotive Network Application.

The Resource Inventory module (which is part of the Resource Orchestration system) continuously keeps updated, using a pub/sub interaction with the Network Management & Service Orchestration (MANO) layer, a list of the available Edge and Far-Edge resources (OBUs/RSUs) to be used as devices to host Network Applications. Therefore, they are part of one or more MicroK8s clusters marked as worker nodes. Figure 4 shows the procedures to register a new cluster to be monitored by the Resource Inventory function. The platform manager (i.e., the Automotive OBUs/RSUs service provider) registers a new set of Edge and Far-Edge resources by providing the references of the MicroK8s Control Plane (the URL of the distributed MicroK8s controller along with the security certificates for authentication). Once a cluster is added to the list of systems under monitoring, an interface with the MANO layer (the list of MicroK8s controllers) is constantly fed with asynchronous notifications whenever a node joins/leaves the system itself.

V. DEPLOYMENT OF AN AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATION: THE REMOTE DRIVING NETWORK APPLICATION

A good example of the successful deployment of automotive applications in the platform is the execution of a remote driving network application over the Nokia testbed located in Ulm, Germany. In this section, the 5G infrastructure and equipment is first presented. The remote driving network application itself is then described.

A. The 5G Infrastructure

The Nokia 5G infrastructure is used to integrate and test the 5G-IANA platform, specifically evaluating the performance of the automotive use cases. Two network slices, dedicated to V2X and eMBB services, were configured. Extensive testing of selected smartphones and 5G modules is conducted in the testbed to ensure compliance with specifications. The evaluation also ensures proper functioning of the Nokia 5GS and assesses network capabilities for the 5G-IANA platform. The central unit of gNB in the Nokia laboratory connects to the four antenna sites via optical cables. UPFs responsible for routing user data and the EDGE Server hosting Data Networks for 5G-IANA use cases are also located in the Nokia laboratory. The co-location of these components, coupled with optical fiber use, results in user data traffic latency below 1ms between antenna sites and the EDGE Server. A server meeting 5G-IANA project partner requirements, equipped with AMD Ryzen 9 5900X CPU, NVIDIA RTX 3080 TI GPU, 128GB RAM, 2TB SSD, 8TB HDD, 2*10G SFP+ NIC, and running Ubuntu server 22.04 LTS, serves as the EDGE Server. Nokia initially utilized frequencies in the 700MHz (band n28) and 3.6 GHz (band n78) ranges, offering excellent coverage with good throughput rates and high throughput rates with limited coverage, respectively. Network Slicing is employed to allocate resources for specific services, ensuring isolated network resources for quality service. Nokia provides two preconfigured network slices for eMBB and V2X services, each tailored to meet specific use case requirements.

Fig. 5. Autonomous guided vehicle equipped with OBU, 5G modem, two cameras and a LiDAR.

B. The Remote driving Network Application

One of the main successful on-boarding and validation activities of a network application in the platform was performed for a remote driving use case. A real-time demonstration of a remote driving service including 360° LiDAR information and ML video-based object detection was deployed by the platform orchestrator and demonstrated live in the Nokia 5G testbed. In this demonstration, the AGV shown in Figure 5 and equipped with an OBU, both front and rear cameras, the LiDAR and a modem was controlled via 5G by a remote driver. The driver was also connected through a 5G modem and received the processed video as well as some key warning alerts. Based on the inputs received, the driver provided the orders to move the vehicle throughout driving peripherals (wheel and pedals). The remote driving application itself is formed by five main NFs, i.e., the video encoder and transmitter deployed at the OBU, the ML algorithm that generates warnings about elements surrounding the vehicle (pedestrians, vehicles, traffic signs) based on the video input, a video server to decode and stream to the user interface, a vehicle communication API for providing/receiving driving commands and sensors data, and a component running the graphical user interface. This graphical interface is shown in Figure 6.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper has described how a reliable, highly available, and distributed Network Application orchestration system enables the possibility of onboarding, deploying, and testing Automotive-oriented services on top of an infrastructure composed of a set of Edge and Far-Edge devices affected by the potential discontinuity of mobile connectivity. The AOEP aims to promote the development of new vertical automotive services that can leverage the performance and functionality offered by 5G mobile networks. End-users can also experience distributed machine learning (DML) services through the DML Orchestration layer, which is part of the AOEP. Other layers of the AOEP include the monitoring and analysis layer and the distributed data collection layer, used for application profiling, tracking faults and misbehaviors, and feeding, through the mediation of the DML Orchestrator, a Policy Manager module to enforce lifecycle actions executed by the Application Orchestrator. The AOEP was designed to operate on different virtualized infrastructure segments to better suit the diverse contexts in which vertical automotive services may run. Future work includes optimizing the software module described in this

Fig. 6. Remote driving network application running at the 5G edge in Nokia testbed.

paper whenever a new set of requirements is defined during the third-party experimentation phase. Moreover, new services and AI algorithms will be generated to demonstrate the impact of the 5G-IANA platform in the automotive sector

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